

THE FIRST SUCCESSFUL MULTI-STAGE HYDRAULIC FRACTURING WITH INSTALLATION OF THE ASSEMBLY IN A CASED HOLE IN A VERTICAL WELL**Suleimenova R.,***Phd***Mussin A.,***2nd year Master's degree of the faculty of Oil and Gas***Sarkulov A.,***2nd year Master's degree of the faculty of Oil and Gas***Shora Zh.***3rd year student of the faculty of Oil and Gas**Atyrau University of Oil and Gas named after Safi Utebayev***Abstract**

This article presents the results of the first multi-stage hydraulic fracturing in a vertical well at a field in the Aktobe region. The field has been developed by one production facility since the beginning of development. The total height of the deposits in some places reaches up to 400 m; accordingly, from the beginning of development, all productive layers were perforated into a continuous one. Test work was carried out on a perforated well with a total thickness of up to 182 meters, which opened four productive formations. In order to open all productive layers with fractures and involve them in development, it was decided to use a 4-stage arrangement with a hydraulic fracturing coupling system with a repeated opening/closing cycle. As a result, after multi-stage hydraulic fracturing using this technology, a 4-fold increase in oil production was obtained. In the future, it is planned to use this method on other candidate wells in the field.

Keywords: Multi-stage hydraulic fracturing, permeability, fracture, conductivity, skin factor, oil content, Upper Permian sediments.

Difficulties in field development

Industrial development of the field began in 2003. In the technological development scheme, based on the location of productive strata, the size and initial geological reserves, as well as taking into account the physical and chemical properties of oil and the geological and hydrodynamic characteristics of reservoirs, several formations were combined into one production facility, having a high coefficient of dissection.

As experience in the development of multilayer objects shows, certain difficulties arise in the process of developing such objects. When several layers are combined into one development object, the direct relationship between the amount of fluid coming from the layers and their hydraulic conductivity is broken. In wells where high-permeability and low-permeability formations are combined under a single filter, the latter, as a rule, are not drained or are drained very poorly.

It has been established that specific productivity coefficients (productivity per 1 m of oil-saturated thickness) for wells of multi-layer objects are significantly lower than the average values for wells that were exploited in individual layers. This shows that not all layers opened in a multi-layer object are working. In addition, the layers operate asynchronously, i.e. the rate of depletion of the reserves contained in them is different. As a result, individual layers are depleted faster and, subsequently, water flows through them into production wells, which does not perform useful work to displace oil from the porous medium. This leads to a decrease in the technological and economic efficiency of developing an operational facility. Therefore, to regulate the development process, measures were taken to introduce methods and technologies at the field that would largely avoid negative consequences, which was associated with the project for the large-scale implementation of hydraulic fracturing.

Figure 1 - Seismic profile

In the period until 2016, only 4 hydraulic fracturing operations were carried out at the field, in two of which STOP was obtained, as a result of which the work was carried out unsuccessfully.

The reasons for the low efficiency of hydraulic fracturing were the following factors:

1) Uncontrolled crack growth

- 2) Initiation of several conflicting cracks (Figure 2)
- 3) Loss of efficiency of hydraulic fracturing fluid
- 4) Incomplete coverage of fractures in all productive formations (fractures developed mainly in the upper formations, the lower ones remained not involved in development) (Figure 3)

Figure 2 - Formation of cracks during extended perforation of multilayer horizons

Selection of multi-stage hydraulic fracturing technology

In order to improve the quality of work and increase the success of hydraulic fracturing operations, quality control and engineering support for hydraulic fracturing were introduced, during which only 13 hydraulic fracturing operations were performed with high

effect. However, due to the presence of perforated intervals with an effective thickness of up to 200 m, it was not possible to solve the problem of fracture coverage of all productive deposits.

To solve this problem, a method was proposed for installing a multi-stage hydraulic fracturing assembly in an already cased wellbore. The work was important

for obtaining additional production, unlocking the potential of multi-stage hydraulic fracturing at the wells of the KTM fields, involving in the development of all

productive formations and conducting interval hydrodynamic studies and taking deep samples.

Figure 3 – Propagation of cracks previously carried out by hydraulic fracturing

After a review of existing multi-stage hydraulic fracturing technologies, a configuration with a full-bore completion system with drillable hydraulic fracturing ports was selected (Figure 4). This system had the following operational advantages:

1. High probability of initiation and development of cracks in target intervals.
2. The ability to control the development of cracks in height, which will depend on the hydraulic fracturing design and layout.
3. Coverage of all productive horizons with fractures due to multi-stage hydraulic fracturing.
4. Reducing the time for multi-stage hydraulic fracturing.

5. Activation with soluble balls
6. The anchor system of the shank allows it to rotate during descent
7. Packers are designed to ensure trouble-free running and prevent unauthorized packing
8. The ability to re-open and close circulation windows during well operation, which allows you to regulate the well's flow rate depending on the quality of the inflow (when one or more intervals are flooded)
9. Possibility of additional approaches after completion of work
10. Ensuring the operation of all opened intervals

Figure 4 – Design of multi-stage hydraulic fracturing assembly

Well No. 108 was selected for experimental work, according to the following criteria:

1. Suitable well design. The production casing is 177.8 mm, which makes it possible to lower the multi-stage hydraulic fracturing assembly.

2. Potential for increased production. The well was carried out in 2017. An increase in oil volume of 10 tons/day was obtained. Availability of growth potential from hydraulic fracturing.

3. Reservoir properties. According to geology, the well is located in a zone of deteriorated reservoir properties.

4. Partial operation of perforation intervals. The total number of existing perforation intervals was 11 intervals, with a total thickness of up to 182m. Based on the results of determining the inflow profile, only 43% of perforation intervals worked.

5. Profitability of potential growth. The economic efficiency of multistage hydraulic fracturing using the layout was calculated; as a result, PI was equal to 2.98

(above 1) and it was decided that the project is profitable.

Carrying out multi-stage hydraulic fracturing

One of the main and decisive factors for the success of the multi-stage hydraulic fracturing operation was the containment of fractures in isolated productive intervals in order to prevent interference of fractures with each other, which could lead to uncontrolled losses of hydraulic fracturing fluid and undesirable complications. Based on the lithologic-petrophysical model, using the results of modeling mechanical properties, the propagation of hydraulic fractures in height was assessed (Figure 5), which made it possible to develop an optimal design of multi-stage hydraulic fracturing in order to retain fractures in productive intervals, as well as ensure the greatest half-length of the fracture and stimulated formation volume. The optimal intervals for inserting sleeves (respectively, places of fracture initiation), volumes of proppant and hydraulic fracturing fluid were determined to ensure high production rates (Table 1).

Table 1

MSHF design parameters				
Parameter	1 stage	2 stage	3 stage	4 stage
Proppant weight, t	20 (16/30)	35 (16/30 – 30) (12/18 – 5)	40 (16/30 - 34) (12/18 – 6)	40 (16/30 – 34) (12/18 – 6)
Volume "pillows", m ³	15	26	30	30
Total volume of liquid, m ³	106	145	156	155
Flow, m ³ /min	4	4	4	4
Max. proppant concentration, kg/m ³	1000	1000	1000	1000

Figure 5 – Design profiles of MSHF fractures

The hydraulic fracturing operation at each of the 4 stages was carried out according to the following scheme:

1. Fitting the ball into the clutch seat with indication on the pressure graph (Fig. 6)

2. Mini-fracturing (carried out selectively - at stages 1 and 3 due to the convergence of reservoir conditions)

3. Basic hydraulic fracturing operation

Figure 6 – Graphs indicating the ball is seated in the clutch seat

After mini-fracturing, data analysis and model adaptation were performed. Hydraulic fracturing to the values of pressure, fracturing fluid efficiency, ISIP (instantaneous closure pressure), etc. obtained in real conditions (Table 2). Based on the adapted model, the design of the main hydraulic fracturing was adjusted.

The main stages of hydraulic fracturing were carried out according to the work plan without any complications. The dynamics of the main hydraulic fracturing indicators are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Hydraulic fracturing schedules

Table 2

Parameters of the performed hydraulic fracturing

Parameter	1 stage	2 stage	3 stage	4 stage
Proppant weight, t	20 (16/30)	34 (16/30 – 30) (12/18 – 4)	40 (16/30 - 34) (12/18 – 6)	40 (16/30 – 34) (12/18 – 6)
Volume "pillows", m3	16	27	30	30
Total volume of liquid, m3	106	114	157	129
Flow, m3/min	4	4	4	4
Max. proppant concentration, kg/m3	1000	1000	1000	1000

After multi-stage hydraulic fracturing, fracture models were calibrated and adapted based on the actual wellhead pressure values obtained as a result of the main injection. Calculations of fracture geometries using the adapted model showed that there was no fracture interference between intervals, and the design parameters of the multi-stage hydraulic fracturing design were achieved. An important part of the successful implementation of multi-stage hydraulic fracturing was the final set of works, which included drilling out the hydraulic fracturing coupling seats to full bore size, injecting nitrogen for flushing and development, and lowering the ESP for complete development. A sampling and well testing study is currently pending using tools to open and close the couplings.

Analysis of the work carried out

As a result, after a successful multi-stage hydraulic fracturing operation with installation of the assembly in a cased-hole vertical well, the following goals were achieved:

➤ After the event, a 4-fold increase in production was obtained (Figure 8).

➤ During hydraulic fracturing, all productive formations are covered: I, II, III, IV.

➤ After completion of development, it is planned to conduct interval sampling of deep samples and further hydrodynamic studies.

Based on the results of the completed set of works, it is planned to carry out similar work at other wells.

Figure 8 – oil production before and after multi-stage hydraulic fracturing

For further application of multi-stage hydraulic fracturing technology, the following factors must be taken into account:

1. Re-completion of existing wells for selective treatment (intensification) and production - a proven solution for wells in several opened productive intervals and simultaneous production

2. Ensuring a full-bore internal diameter of the liner (fracturing sleeves) while minimizing costs - complete elimination of the milling stage (high costs for milling assembly with workover or coiled tubing, additional fluid losses when milling into the formation after stimulation - reduced efficiency of hydraulic fracturing due to clogging during development wells)

3. In order to monitor the productivity of wells and make decisions on regulating the flow rate from various intervals, it is necessary to develop a solution for determining the quality of the inflow, for example, installing tracer systems simultaneously in the completion system to determine the quality of the inflow from each interval at the wellhead (a separate tracer for each interval).

Conclusion

Successful pilot work showed that multi-stage hydraulic fracturing using the installation of an assembly in a cased hole in an old well is possible and this opens up a new opportunity for the development of existing mature fields with long productive intervals with an effective thickness of more than 100 meters. The correct approach to candidate well selection, preparatory and completion work, and the use of high-quality completion technology and multi-stage hydraulic fracturing

have increased the likelihood of success in the field located in Western Kazakhstan.

This exemplary work has shown that the installation of multi-stage hydraulic fracturing is an effective technology not only in horizontal open-hole wells, but also in older cased wells, and is a proven method for well re-completion.

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